

ATMOSPHERIC PLASMA TREATED VGCF/PP NANOCOMPOSITES BY MELT-MIXING PROCESS

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SUMMARY

The raw vapor grown carbon fibers (VGCF) and atmospheric plasma treated (APT) VGCF/PP were fabricated by the melt-mixing process, respectively. The effect of atmospheric plasma treatments on the mechanical properties of VGCF/PP was investigated. The tensile modulus and strength of APT VGCF/PP showed higher value than those of raw VGCF/PP.

Keywords: VGCF, PP, atmospheric plasma treatment, melt-mixing process, mechanical properties

INTRODUCTION

There are increasing interests of vapor grown carbon nanofibers (VGCFs) for the reinforcements of polymeric materials due to their excellent mechanical, electrical, and thermal properties. In the processing of nanocomposites, their bulk properties are not only the functions of the state of fiber dispersion and orientation, but also the interface between the fiber and matrix. VGCFs have been used to reinforce a variety of thermoplastic and thermosetting polymers. Compared with the micro-sized carbon fibers, nanofibers are favorable in the type of thermoplastic compounding owing to the less fiber breakage and the higher aspect ratio. Processing of thermoplastics provides additional advantages of recycling, cost-effectiveness, and environmental benefits due to free of solvents [1]. Among several processing methods for thermoplastic materials, melt-mixing of nanofibers into composites by extrusion process has captured considerable interest. In this process, an extruder die consists of funnel-shaped portion and annular portion, which generates converging flow and shear flow patterns in producing fiber alignment. The process variables of extrusion include the length, the diameter, and the temperature of the nozzle exit. The longer nozzle of an extruder die gave higher tensile modulus and strength due to the better fiber alignment in the extended length [2]. Most of previous works on nanocomposites utilizing the melt-mixing process studied fiber weight fraction up to 15%. While the observed tensile modulus and strength improved significantly in the case of 11% vol [2], the further enhancement is likely if more fibers are added. Among other post-processing methods, the fiber spinning by a spinneret demonstrated the potential of structural usage of nanocomposites [3, 4]. With only 5% fiber volume content of VGCFs/PP, the tensile strength and modulus increased by 16% and 54%, respectively, and the compressive

strength was doubled to that of neat PP material [3]. To ensure a good adhesion between the nanofibers and the polymer matrix a modification of fiber surfaces is necessary. Various methods have been reported to modify the surface of carbon fibers, such as the chemical treatment, thermal treatment, and plasma treatment [5, 6]. The VGCF was treated with atmospheric plasma enhancing the surface area and the compatibility with the matrix.

Materials

The VGCFs were from Showa Denko KK. VGCF had specific surface areas of $13 \text{ m}^2/\text{g}$, the diameter and the length were 150 nm and $10\sim 20 \text{ }\mu\text{m}$, respectively. The real density and bulk density of VGCF were 2.0 g/cm^3 and 0.04 g/cm^3 , respectively. The aspect ratio was 60 with highly crystalline carbon nanofibers synthesized by the gas phase method. Polypropylene powders from Honam Petrochemical Corp. (Korea) were used as a matrix. The specific weight of PP was $0.95 \text{ (g/cm}^3\text{)}$, the diameter was $0.5\sim 1.0 \text{ mm}$, the melting point was 170°C , and the molecular weight was 10,000.

Plasma Treatment of VGCF

The atmospheric plasma treatment (ATP) can be used to improve the roughness and surface area of VGCF in order to increase the interfacial bonding between VGCF and PP. As shown in Fig.1, VGCF was plasma treated in an atmospheric glow discharge reactor. Helium was used as a carrier gas and no monomer was used to modify the surface property by plasma polymerization. The electrodes were inductively connected around the reactor tube, and the frequency and the voltage were 20 kHz and 3 kV , respectively.

Figure 1: Continuous process of plasma treatment for VGCF

Fabrication of VGCF/PP nanocomposites

To produce raw VGCF/PP and APT VGCF/PP by melt-mixing process (up to 40 wt%), the VGCF's were sonicated in ethanol for 10 min using the Sonic Mater[®] sonicator. The

solution contained more than 20 ml of ethanol per 1g of VGCF. The PP powder was then added and mixed under continuous mechanical mixing for an additional hour. The ethanol was dried out and the remaining portion was removed by the vacuum extraction at 80°C for 48 h. The PP powder matrix was melt-mixed by twin-screw extruder (PRIM TSC 16 TC, Thermo Electron Corp.), and then the rod was extruded with a diameter of 1.0 mm. The temperatures of five extruder sections from first heating zone to the die were set as 180, 230, 230, 230, and 200°C, respectively. The hopper rate, the screw speed, and the speed of roll were adequately adjusted for this process. Increasing the middle section temperature of heating zone also helped to decrease the viscosity of VGCF/PP. The weight contents of VGCF varied from 0.0 to 40.0wt%. The temperature of die was set at 250°C for 0.0 to 23.0 wt% of VGCF, and the temperature was decreased to 200°C for 29.0 and 50 wt% of VGCF, respectively. As the VGCF weight contents increased, the higher temperatures of the die did not result in good rod shape. After extrusion, the VGCF/PP rods were vacuum dried at 90°C for 12 h. The panel was molded into a 250x80 mm² mold. The thickness of panel of VGCF/PP was controlled by the stopper trip in the mold. The molding condition is shown in Fig. 2. The sample thickness was in the range of 3.0-3.2 mm.

Figure 2: Fabrication cycle for VGCF/PP.

VGCFs at levels of 9-40wt% contents were mixed with PP powder, and then were melt-mixed by a twin-screw extruder. For the further alignment of fibers, the extruded rods were stacked unidirectionally in a mold cavity for the compression moulding. Melt-mixing was conducted on a twin-screw extruder. With the opening of 0.5 mm, the continuous composites rods of consistent diameter have been fabricated (Fig. 3).

Mechanical Tests

The specimens for tensile, flexural, and shear strength tests were prepared in accordance with ASTM D638 Type IV, ASTM D790M and ASTM D5379, respectively. The tensile and flexural specimen dimensions were 3.0 x 6.0 x 80.0 mm³ and 3.0 x 12.7 x 60.0 mm³, respectively. The shear specimen dimensions were 3.0 x 20 x 76 mm³. Instron 5567 was used for the mechanical tests. In the tensile tests, the extensometer length was 25.0 mm. The machine was operated under the displacement control mode with a speed of 2.00 mm/min. The span used for flexural test was 40.0 mm, the speed for flexural test was 1.00 mm/min. The strain gauges with 5.0 mm lengths were used for

the shear test specimens, and the speed for shear test was 2.00 mm/min. Minimum of five specimens were prepared from each panel for each condition.

Figure 3: Extruded rods and fibers.

Tensile modulus and strength of VGCF/PP

The tensile modulus in longitudinal direction of APT VGCF/PP with 9.0, 23.0, 29.0 and 40.0 VGCF wt% were increased by 123.8, 135.2, 169.1 and 108.9 % than those of raw VGCF, respectively. The tensile modulus in transverse direction of APT VGCF/PP with 9.0, 23.0, 29.0 and 40.0 wt% were 190, 133, 152 and 121 % greater than those of raw VGCF, respectively (Fig. 4).

The tensile strength in longitudinal direction of APT VGCF/PP with 23.0, 29.0, and 40.0 VGCF wt% were increased by 16.5, 63.3 and 13.5 % than those of raw VGCF/PP, respectively. The tensile strengths in transverse direction APT VGCF/PP were higher than that of raw VGCF/PP with the same VGCF contents (Fig. 4).

Shear properties of raw VGCF/PP and APT VGCF/PP

The shear modulus in transverse direction (T-shear modulus) and the shear strength in transverse direction (T-shear strength) with various VGCF contents are shown in Fig. 5. The T-shear modulus of raw VGCF/PP matrix was increased with increasing VGCF contents up to 40.0 wt%. The T-shear modulus of APT VGCF/PP with 9.0, 23.0, 29.0 and 40.0 wt% VGCF contents were increased by 70.0, 68.4, 66.3 and 43.4% compared with those of raw VGCF/PP, respectively. The optimal VGCF contents for APT VGCF/PP was found to be 40.0 wt%.

The ratio of T-shear strength of APT VGCF/PP and T-shear strength of raw VGCF/PP were 1.71, 1.29, 1.43, and 1.39 with 9.0, 23.0, 29.0 and 40.0 wt% VGCF contents, respectively. Thus, the atmospheric plasma treatment had improved the interfacial bonding between VGCF and PP.

SEM micrographs

Fig. 6 shows SEM micrographs of fractured surfaces of a VGCF/PP composite rod (29 wt%) in the perpendicular to the extrusion direction. Entanglement of VGCF was hardly seen, indicating fairly uniform fiber distribution. Although shear flow occurred in

entering annular portion of the extruder die, fiber arrangement was not fully aligned as shown in Fig. 6 (b). This is due to the fact that fibers of smaller aspect ratio tend to be positioned in three-dimensional arrangement. However, section in the longitudinal direction shows relatively better alignment as shown in Fig. 6 (c).

Figure 4(1): (a) L-tensile modulus of APT VGCF/PP, (b) L-tensile modulus of raw VGCF/PP, T-tensile modulus of APT VGCF/PP, (d) T-tensile modulus of raw VGCF/PP; Figure 4(2): (e) L-tensile strength of APT VGCF/PP, (f) L-tensile strength of raw VGCF/PP, (g) T-tensile strength of APT VGCF/PP, (h) T-tensile strength of raw VGCF/PP.

L: Longitudinal, T: Transverse.

Figure 5: (a) T-shear modulus of raw VGCF/PP, (b) T-shear strength of raw VGCF/PP, (c) T-shear modulus of APT VGCF/PP, (d) T-shear strength of APT VGCF/PP

Figure 6: SEM of VGCF 29 % wt /PP: (a), (b) cross-section; (c) longitudinal section.

Conclusion

The atmospheric plasma treatments were conducted with helium to modify the surface properties of VGCF in order to improve the interfacial bonding with PP. Raw VGCF and APT VGCF were dispersed uniformly throughout the PP by means of melt blending with a twin-screw extruder.

The atmospheric plasma treatments have improved mechanical properties of VGCF/PP. The tensile modulus and strength, shear modulus and strength of APT VGCF/PP were higher than those of raw VGCF/PP. This may be due to the enhancement of the compatibility between VGCF and PP. The twin-screw extruder process provided good dispersion and improved the alignment of VGCF's in PP.

The optimal VGCF contents for APT VGCF/PP was found to be 29.0 wt%, which provided the highest tensile modulus and strength as compared to the other VGCF contents.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the Korea Foundation for Int'l Cooperation of Science & Technology (KICOS) through a grant provided by the Korea Ministry of Education, Science & Technology (MEST), No. K20704000090

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